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Organizational Culture in University: A Bibliometric Analysis

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Abstract

Organizational culture as one of the important factors in the organization is a theme often discussed in the research. Many make organizational culture a variable which is then linked to other variables. Therefore, organizational culture research needs to be done to determine whether this topic is still relevant for research. In this paper, researchers are interested in seeing whether organizational culture is still a topic that still needs to be studied, especially organizational culture in universities. Given the times and the factors of external and internal organizational change, the question of organizational culture has become a topic that deserves further discussion. For this reason, research on the development trend of "Organizational Culture at the University" as a research theme is necessary. The method used is the Scopus search engine in random journals to identify related publications. Organizational culture is used as the main search keyword. The data obtained is then exported in RIS format and analyzed to obtain a research development map. The study also used data visualization software called VOSviewer to analyze the results, underlying relationships, and developing trends. The main finding of this study indicates that organizational culture in universities is experiencing a downward trend, and not many studies have addressed this theme. Hence this finding may be useful for similar research in the future.

Keywords: Organization Culture, University, VOSviewer

1. Introduction

Globalization, pandemics and technological advances encourage changes and developments in the business and socio-economic environment. Organizations are required to always adapt and develop along with changing times. Changes in an organization cannot be separated from the role of organizational culture. Organizational culture supports the organization to be able to achieve its goals. Culture in organizations represents a set of perceptions, memories, beliefs, attitudes, and definitions created by consensus (Baek & Kim, 2019). In addition, culture is seen as a competitive advantage that can be managed and changed. Organizational culture is a significant topic of

discussion in the business literature. Organizational culture is formed because of the performance, creativity, motivation of the organization (Selvi & Murthy, 2021). There are two approaches to the study of culture in the organizational context. In the first approach, culture is considered as an organizational variable that can be manipulated and interpreted. Leaders can influence the nature, direction, and impact of organizational culture. In the second approach, organizational culture is seen as an integral part of the thoughts, feelings, and actions of the organization and leaders are influenced by it. In this approach, leaders can help shape, develop, and preserve a culture in accordance with organizational goals (Hosseini et al., 2019).

1.1 *Statement of the problem*

Gorzelay, et al. (2021), in their research, states that organizational culture in universities is a way for universities to achieve their goals and is the basis for decision making. By understanding the importance of organisational culture, the researcher wants to explore other aspects by showing whether this important organizational culture is still a topic that many researchers are studying. The present article concerns organizational culture, especially on organizational culture at universities, which is minimal. Although the discussion about organizational culture starts from the definition, theory development, characteristics, etc., as well as many studies examining organisational culture's influence on competitive advantage, employees' behaviors, innovation, etc., empirical support is still limited (Aboramadan et al., 2020). This study addresses conceptual gaps observed in the previous studies.

2. **Literature Review**

2.1 *Organization culture*

Organizational culture is defined by values and employee behaviors that contribute to the organizational environment and influence both internal and external behaviors of organization (Wu et al., 2019). Organization culture is described as a system of behaviors, values and meanings including visible symbols, communication and orientations to change (Bakhri, Udin, Daryono, & Suharnomo, 2018; Maryati, Astuti, & Udin, 2019; Smollan & Morrison, 2019). The discussion of organizational culture at universities is not much different from the perspective on organizational culture presented by Quinn's (1988) organizational culture model which divides organizational culture into four types of culture; Clan, Adhocracy, Market and Hierarchy (Bamber, 2020). Clan culture is like a family, this culture focuses on teamwork, parenting and mentoring by leaders to subordinates, and has a strong tradition and employee loyalty (AlDari et al., 2020). Adhocracy culture is considered a more open system with values that involve external relationships in a flexible organizational structure. In an adhocracy culture, creativity, transformation, and growth values, which enable members to cope with environmental changes actively, are highly emphasized. A market culture emphasises stability and control and gives more attention to the organization's external environment. A hierarchy culture is more about stability, control and focus on the organization's internal environment (Balaji et al., 2020).

2.2 *Organization culture in university*

Organisational culture is an important feature in management. In higher education institutions, organisational culture is based on practices and influenced by traditions, norms and controlling individuals' and groups' behaviour (Mzangwa & Serpa, 2019). Organizational culture influences individual behaviors and can be used to understand commitment, job satisfaction, self-efficacy, and collective efficacy (Zain-Ul-Abidin et al., 2020). Culture is a social product of an intentional or unintentional social interaction behavior. Educational Institution's culture is different from other organizational cultures because of its impact on teacher's and student's learning (Kareem et al., 2022).

3. **Method**

This paper uses a qualitative method with a literature study to know research trends regarding "Organizational Culture" by analyzing related documents in the Scopus database search. To obtain a map of research developments, the data is exported in RIS format. The exported data is then processed and analyzed using the VOSViewer

application program to find out the bibliometric map of "Organizational culture in university."

3.1 Research method

Qualitative research examines the condition of natural objects where the researcher is the key instrument of this research, data collection techniques are carried out by triangulation (combined), data analysis is inductive, and research results emphasize meaning rather than generalization. Literature study carried out by reading works related to the problem to be studied and noting important parts that have to do with the topic to be discussed (Sembiring, 2021) Literature study is research that collects data and combines data obtained from related works that have been read and studied. It can be concluded that research using qualitative methods with literature study is research that collects data and combines data obtained from related works that have been read and studied. In this paper, data were obtained from Scopus in May 2022. The initial search identified publications related to policy research in the title, abstract, or keywords: (organization AND culture AND on AND university AND culture AND university AND organization) AND (LIMIT-TO (OA , "all")) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2018)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBSTAGE , "final")) AND (LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD , "Organizational Culture") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTKEYWORD , "University")) so that it got 118 Articles, 11 Reviews, 8 Editorials, 6 Notes, and 2 Conference Papers. The selected articles are then categorized and reviewed using VosViewer. Scopus was chosen because it has an internationally recognized quality and reputation both by universities and research institutions and the use of Vosviewer as data processing software because it has advantages in mapping and visualizing its data. large bibliometric map can be easily displayed and interpreted the relations via the VOSViewer. There are several important characteristics including various types of bibliometric analysis mapping, supporting major bibliographic databases, being limited to analyzing small to medium amounts of data, cluster and layout techniques, with overlay and density visualization features (Bayu et al., n.d.)

4. Results

4.1 Data by Scopus

Scientific writing articles discussing quality continued to decline during 2018-2022. A total of 145 articles have been published while in 2022 only 5 articles. With many new research themes emerging as well as developing issues and the existence of a pandemic being the theme that dominates research these years. However, 2019 became the year where Organizational Culture at the University became a theme that was again used by many researchers. This is in accordance with Figure 1 which shows a decline in the writing of scientific articles with a focus on writing Organizational Culture in Higher Education. This decrease shows that there are not many researchers who are conducting research on organizational culture, especially organizational culture at universities.

Figure 1: Trends in Research Documents in 2018-2022

When viewed based on the source, research on organizational culture at universities is widely published in health journals, whereas in economic journals which generally discuss organizational culture, not much is done. In Figure 2, it can be seen that the sources of most articles published by the International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health are 8 documents/articles, Plos One as many as 8 documents/articles, Academic Medicine as many as 7 documents/articles, BMC Health Services Research as many as 6 documents/articles. articles, and the American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education as many as 4 documents/articles.

Figure 2: Documents by Source

Research on culture in this organization is important because it can make a positive contribution to future researchers. These researchers use previous research as a basis for developing theories and conducting other forms of research. It is undeniable that in this case the amount of research that is available and can be accessed by prospective researchers is very important. In Figure 3, there are several researchers who examine organizational culture at universities and often become a reference for new researchers. These researchers, on average, write more than 1 research article that can be used as a reference. Some of them such as Bowman, T.G. and Singe, S.M. have written 3 documents regarding Organization Culture on University. While the rest of the researchers have published 2 research documents.

Figure 3: Documents by Author

Affiliation is very influential on the type of journal that will be published. For example, in business schools, the journals produced are journals with research on business and economics, while schools related to health will do more research on the theme of health. In this case, organizational culture, especially in universities, is a common theme that can be researched, although the affiliations are different. This is because of the relevance of organizational culture that includes all types of organizations.

Documents by affiliation

Compare the document counts for up to 15 affiliations.

Figure 4: Documents by Affiliation

Based on affiliations or inter-institutional relationships in Figure 4, most documents were obtained from John Hopkins School of Medicine, University of Glasgow, Baylor College of Medicine, Arizona School of Health Sciences, Stanford University, Imperial College London, University of Toronto, University of Connecticut, University of Colorado School of Medicine as many as 3 documents and the University of Lynchburg as many as 2 documents. As seen in Figure 5, the countries with the most research publication with the theme of organizational culture at universities are from the United States, followed by the United Kingdom.

Documents by country or territory

Compare the document counts for up to 15 countries/territories.

Figure 5: Documents by Country

4.2 Data by VOSviewer

Of the 145 documents obtained in the Scopus database search, these documents were exported to RIS format, then inputted and bibliometric analysis was carried out using VOSviewer to find out the bibliometric network that existed between the downloaded data. From the analysis results imported into VOSviewer generated overlay visualization. In this visualization, the color of the node represents the keyword, as well as the year the article was published containing that keyword. The darker the color on the node, the longer the topic is discussed in research. The size of the circle indicates the number of publications related to the word, both in the title and in the abstract of the article. The larger the circle, the greater the number of articles related to the word. In Figure 6 it can also be seen that "organizational culture in university," is divided into 5 clusters.

every year, with the exception of 2019, which experienced an increase.

2. The International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health is the largest journal that publishes 8 documents/articles, while the American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education only publishes 4 documents/articles.
3. America is the country with the most publications and Indonesia is the country with the fewest publications
4. Network visualization shows that the relationship between topics is shown by a line between descriptors in each field. The more lines of relationship between descriptors, the closer the relationship between documents. Meanwhile, density visualization shows that the relationship between topics with color visualization is getting yellower, indicating that the topic has been widely studied, while if the color visualization is getting greener then the topic is still rarely studied.

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